

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets

D1.4 Use cases

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASHP	Air Source Heat Pump
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BO	Business Objective
COP	Coefficient of Performance
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DT	Digital Twin
EMS	Energy Management System
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NLM	Natural Language Model
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OCPI	Open Charge Point Interface
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RH	Relative Humidity
R-ID	Requirement ID
SHC	Social Housing Company
SOC	State of Charge
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D1.4 – Use Cases presents the methodology and results of the work carried out to identify, describe, and formalise the Use Cases (UCs) that will guide the development and validation of the EU-DREAM platform. Aligned with IEC 62559-2:2015, this document ensures a structured, harmonised approach across all project partners.

The work builds upon the six Living Labs (LL1–LL6) established in Portugal, Belgium, Italy, Ireland, Greece, and Denmark. Each Living Lab represents a specific testing or co-creation environment reflecting different climatic, technological, and social contexts. Together, they enable the assessment of EU-DREAM innovations in real-world conditions and support the scalability and replicability of the proposed solutions.

The document first outlines the context and objectives of each Living Lab (LL), including stakeholders, assets, and monitoring infrastructures. It then introduces the methodology for UC development. Each UC has been structured using a harmonised template covering objectives, actors, scenarios, pre- and post-conditions, requirements, and related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The resulting set of UCs forms the baseline for the design and validation of the EU-DREAM platform, ensuring traceability from user needs and business objectives to the technical implementation.

Overall, D1.4 provides the methodological and conceptual foundation for subsequent technical, social, and business developments, ensuring that innovation within EU-DREAM is validated through participatory, real-life experimentation across Europe’s diverse Living Lab network.

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Introduction

EU-DREAM – Effective Uptake of Digital services to Repower European consumers and communities as Active participants in energy transition and Markets – aims to place citizens at the centre of the future energy ecosystem. The project’s ambition is to make the complexity of energy systems understandable, transparent, and actionable for everyone, enabling consumers to engage confidently with emerging digital energy services.

To achieve this, EU-DREAM introduces a smart digital intermediary, which acts as an energy attorney, bridging the gap between complex energy markets and end-users’ daily experience. By leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI), Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Digital Twin (DT) technologies, the platform translates technical operations and market mechanisms into clear, user-friendly insights and actions. This approach allows citizens to express their energy preferences in plain language, focusing on comfort, cost, and sustainability, while remaining shielded from system-level complexity.

Deliverable D1.4 – Use Cases defines the methodological framework that will guide the design and validation of this vision. It identifies, structures, and documents the technical and social UCs developed within the six EU-DREAM LLs across Europe. These UCs describe how the envisioned platform, tools, and interactions will be implemented and tested in real-life conditions. The next stages of the project will translate these UCs into action through Work Package 7 (WP7), where the concepts and solutions outlined in D1.4 will be implemented and validated.

The structure of the deliverable is designed to guide the reader from a general overview of the LLs to the presentation of the UCs proposed for each of them. Following the description of the six LLs - covering geographic, climatic, technological, and social aspects - the document outlines the identified requirements, business objectives, and the methodology adopted for UC description. To ensure clarity and readability, the main body includes a summary of the UCs per LL. At the same time, the detailed descriptions, both of the LLs’ characteristics and the individual UCs, are provided in the annexes (Annexes A–G). This structure is made to ensure a balance between informational completeness and content accessibility.

Living Labs' Characteristics

A Living Lab (LL) constitutes a real-world environment designed to facilitate experimentation, co-creation, and validation of innovative solutions under actual operating conditions. Within the framework of the project, six LLs will be established across six EU Member States — Portugal, Belgium, Italy, Ireland, Greece, and Denmark — each pursuing specific objectives and thematic priorities.

The solutions developed throughout the project will be validated in five of these LLs, with different levels of integration, maturity, and deployment. In addition, the Belgian LL will engage in co-creation activities with vulnerable households, aiming to identify their needs and motivations in order to inform the development of socially inclusive energy tools.

A comprehensive description of these LLs, listed in Table 1, and their main characteristics are provided in the following sections.

Table 1 – LLs.

LL Number	Description	Location
LL1	AI-Powered Renewable Energy Communities	Coimbra, PORTUGAL
LL2	Energy Poverty and Vulnerable Consumers Impacts	Genk, BELGIUM
LL3	Energy Flexibility at Residential Scale and Interoperability	Northern Italy, ITALY
LL4	Consumers Empowerment for Energy Management	Munster, IRELAND
LL5	Smart Energy Services for Multi-Energy Vectors	Athens, Thessaloniki, Larisa, Volos, GREECE
LL6	DT-enabled Residential IoT Microgrid	Aalborg, DENMARK

General Information

This section provides an overview of the main elements that characterise each LL. It describes the key stakeholders, geographical and climatic conditions, and the typology. These aspects establish the boundary conditions for testing, replication, and evaluation of the EU-DREAM solutions across different European contexts.

Key Stakeholders

Each LL involves a diverse range of stakeholders reflecting the multi-actor nature of the energy ecosystem. These include end users, energy providers, technology suppliers, research institutions, and public authorities. Table 2 summarises the key stakeholder categories engaged across the six LLs (key stakeholders' categorisation is based on (Caliano, et al., 2022)).

Table 2 – Key Stakeholders involved in the LLs.

Key Stakeholders	LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4	LL5	LL6
<i>End users, including consumers and active customers</i>	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>Electricity producers</i>	X	X				
<i>Energy suppliers</i>		X	X	X	X	
<i>Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)</i>		X				
<i>Technology Suppliers</i>	X	X		X		X
<i>Aggregators</i>		X				
<i>Transmission System Operator (TSO)</i>						
<i>Distribution System Operator (DSO)</i>		X				X
<i>Government, policymakers and regulators</i>		X				
<i>Balance the responsible party</i>						
<i>Energy storage owners</i>	X	X				
<i>Non-profit organisations (associations, foundations)</i>		X				
<i>Research actors (Univ., private research institute, etc.)</i>		X	X	X		X
<i>Banks, private investors</i>						
<i>Energy cooperatives</i>						
<i>Local Authorities</i>		X				
<i>Electric vehicle owners</i>	X	X	X			
<i>District heating network operator</i>						

Geographic Region

The six LLs are distributed across different European regions, ensuring a broad representation of geographic and socio-economic contexts. This diversity supports the scalability and transferability of the developed solutions. Table 3 presents the corresponding geographic regions according to the classification made in the Geographic Regions Section (<https://unstats.un.org/unsd/methodology/m49/>)

Table 3 – Geographic Region of LLs.

Geographic Region	LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4	LL5	LL6
<i>Northern Europe</i>				X		X
<i>Eastern Europe</i>						
<i>Southern Europe</i>	X		X		X	
<i>Western Europe</i>		X				

Climatic Conditions

The climatic conditions of each LL area have been identified following the Köppen Climate Classification (Kottek, Grieser, Beck, Rudolf, & Rubel, 2006).

Understanding these environmental characteristics is essential for assessing the performance and adaptability of energy systems under varying temperature, humidity, and seasonal profiles. Table 4 provides an overview of the main climatic types of the LLs.

Table 4 – Climatic Condition of LLs.

LL	Climatic Condition
LL1	Warm-summer Mediterranean climate
LL2	Marine west coast climate: Cfb Temperate climate with no dry season and a warm summer
LL3	Humid Subtropical
LL4	Cfb: Oceanic climate
LL5	Hot-Summer Mediterranean Climate (Csa) - Athens, Larisa, Volos Humid Subtropical Climate (Cfa) - Thessaloniki
LL6	Oceanic/Marine Cfb that Borders on Humid Continental Dfb

Typology

All Living Labs selected Residential as their typology, in line with the different categories (Residential, Commercial, Industrial, Rural). LL6 additionally includes a university environment, alongside its primary residential classification.

User Characteristics and Social Aspects

This section presents a detailed overview of the composition, literacy levels, and engagement dynamics of the users involved in each LL participating in the EU-DREAM.

These values range from small groups of five users or households (LL4, LL6) to larger communities such as LL5, involving about 100 households (approximately 250 individuals), LL1 with around 40 houses, and LL2 with 90 inhabitants. In some cases, such as LL3, the specific user group has not yet been defined and will be identified in later stages of the project.

Table 5 presents the number of users or households participating in each LL, along with the approximate size of the user group. These values range from small groups of five users or households (LL4, LL6) to larger communities such as LL5, involving about 100 households (approximately 250 individuals), LL1 with around 40 houses, and LL2 with 90 inhabitants. In some cases, such as LL3, the specific user group has not yet been defined and will be identified in later stages of the project.

Table 5 – Number of Users of LL / Participants.

LL	Number of Users of Living Lab / Participants
LL1	The LL is in constant change with people entering and leaving. However, we intend to always maintain around 40 houses participating in the tests. We estimate that between 60 and 80 people will be involved.

LL2	90 inhabitants (tenants) involved.
LL3	The first LL setup will be a laboratory carried out by IREN and IME, together with research actors. At the same time, the identification of 1-2 residential homes will be implemented at a later stage of the project, and, accordingly, the user characteristics will be identified. The selection will be based on the results obtained in the LL, following the structural matching prerequisites (EV Charger, remote control, etc.), hence occurring after the completion of setup and testing begins.
LL4	5 households, each with two adults per household, some with children also.
LL5	100 households, with an average of 2.51 people per household, totalling 250 individuals actively participating in the project.
LL6	5 Users

Table 6 reports the average digital literacy of users in each LL, indicating their general level of familiarity and competence with digital technologies across categories such as Nothing, Basic, Intermediate, and Advanced.

These vary across LLs: LL1, LL4 and LL6 involve participants with intermediate/higher digital literacy. In contrast, others (LL2 and LL5) include a broader mix of users, from individuals with limited digital skills to those with advanced technical knowledge. In LL3, digital literacy will be determined once the residential participants are selected.

Table 6 – Average Digital Literacy.

Average Digital Literacy	LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4	LL5	LL6
Nothing						
Basic		X			X	
Intermediate				X		
Advanced	X					X

Table 7 reports the average energy literacy, describing users' general understanding of energy concepts and practices, also classified into the same categories: Nothing, Basic, Intermediate, and Advanced. These vary across LLs: LL1, LL4 and LL6 involve participants with intermediate/higher energy literacy. In contrast, others (LL2 and LL5) include a broader mix of users, from individuals with limited digital skills to those with advanced technical knowledge. In LL3, energy literacy will be determined once the residential participants are selected. Each LL will be accompanied by a short descriptive note explaining the context of the users.

Table 7 - Average Energy Literacy.

Average Energy Literacy	LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4	LL5	LL6
Nothing						
Basic		X			X	
Intermediate	X			X		
Advanced						X

LL1: Since most of the Living Lab members are employees of an energy company (Cleanwatts Digital), they will have a more advanced knowledge about energy topics than the average person.

LL2: An extensive range of people is involved in the LL, which makes it very difficult to indicate the average literacy. Digital Literacy ranges from elderly people with no digital literacy (preferring paper newsletters) to people with advanced digital literacy (asking for an app on their phone to have insight into the PV production). The Energy literacy ranges from people just paying their energy bills without understanding them (already for more than 10 years with the same energy supplier) to people who are well aware of concepts such as the capacity tariff and increasing self-consumption by using energy when the sun is shining.

LL3: The Italian LL, developed within EU-DREAM, combines: i) a from-scratch laboratory testbed and ii) 1–2 real residential homes to evaluate interoperability, flexibility, and remote-control of heterogeneous devices and communication protocols for digital energy services and residential Demand Response. The laboratory simulates a real home environment to test communication standards, device integration, and control strategies under controlled conditions; only after successful validation in the testbed, IREN households — with required structural features such as EV chargers or remote-controllable devices — will be involved in real-world demonstrations. Accordingly, customers and digital-energy literacy will be defined at a later stage, as the procurement process evolves toward its completion. This combined approach ensures technical feasibility, customer acceptability, and supports the exploration of new flexibility-oriented business models.

LL4: The living lab participants are from a variety of backgrounds; two of the five participants are employees of DCSix Technologies. Three of the 5 participants have ASHP installs, so the assumption can be made that their energy literacy will be higher than that of the average homeowner. The same participants are expected to have an intermediate digital literacy given their professions; however, in-depth technical knowledge and understanding regarding digital literacy cannot be confirmed.

LL5: The living lab involves households with diverse backgrounds, socioeconomic situations, and demographic profiles, ranging from young families to elderly residents and from middle-income to more financially constrained groups. Across this diversity, participants generally display basic levels of energy literacy. Most users are comfortable with everyday actions, such as paying energy bills or adjusting heating settings, but have a limited understanding of deeper concepts like dynamic electricity pricing, the efficiency differences between boilers and heat pumps, building thermal behaviour, or how occupancy and weather influence heating demand. Energy decisions are often based on long-standing habits rather than informed optimisation. Although a small subset of participants shows higher awareness, expressing interest in reducing heating bills or recognising the benefits of off-peak operation, the majority do not regularly interpret consumption data or compare tariff structures. This combination of heterogeneous user profiles and overall modest digital and energy literacy highlights the importance of EU-DREAM's simplified interfaces, intuitive insights, and conversational tools to meaningfully engage users and support their transition toward smarter energy behaviours.

LL6: The participants are part of the Laboratory and present advanced digital and energy literacy

Finally, Table 8 will outline the level of engagement and participation within each LL. This encompasses the degree to which users interact with the implemented technologies, participate in co-creation activities, and contribute to decision-making processes. Engagement levels range from limited interaction, where future improvements aim to enhance user involvement through new tools and interfaces (e.g., LL1, LL5), to highly participatory approaches involving community events, co-design workshops, and ongoing communication with residents (LL2). In other cases (LL3 and LL4), engagement is structured around experimental activities, educational initiatives, and feedback collection, while LL6 represents a demonstration environment without permanent users.

Table 8 - Level of engagement and participation.

LL	Current and expected level of engagement
LL1	Currently, most LL members do not interact much with the Energy Management System (EMS) and do not even check the energy measurements being recorded in their homes. With EU-DREAM, it is intended that the user's involvement increase with the simpler and more engaging technologies that will be developed, like the NLP interface. Users are expected to participate in setting parameters, such as the time of day the car should be fully charged and the battery's optimisation goals (e.g., reducing CO ₂ emissions and/or minimising electricity costs).
LL2	All the participants in the OPEN Lab were selected because of their high motivation to be part of the energy transition and to test new energy technologies. Following the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry, an intensive participatory trajectory was set up with the inhabitants. This trajectory, which is still ongoing, includes co-creation sessions, info sessions, festive events, home visits, site visits... However, throughout the renovation process, this motivation was challenged multiple times (due to delays and hindrances). Therefore, the current challenge is to regain their trust and maintain high motivation during the operational phase of LL. The key is to avoid an overload of questions or information while engaging them and giving them ownership. The interaction with the inhabitants in the operational phase of the LL is still to be defined. A recurring meeting, at least on an annual basis, will be set up to inform the participants of the latest state of affairs. In addition to this, an interaction medium (dashboard, app, chat group) will be set up to inform people about the measurement results of their houses and to capture questions, concerns, and other feedback.
LL3	The testbed lab is designed to simulate a home environment where users can perform their daily activities, using appliances as they normally would. In the "real environment" laboratory, end-user engagement and participation are required. In particular, end-users will carry out their everyday tasks in their homes, using appliances tailored to their individual requirements and limitations. Its purpose is to observe how users interact with appliances in a natural setting, based on their daily needs and constraints. The "real environment" lab will allow control of various home appliances. Data on user experience when controlling smart home devices will be gathered. Moreover, users will be integrated into the decision-making process through the AI-based Assistant Tool, which will enable them to share their input on decisions, provide feedback, offer suggestions, and preferences at key stages.

LL4	The DCSix LL is conceived to empower real consumers for energy management and to facilitate their active participation in the just energy transition (related to WP1), testing their impact on energy consumption and production patterns. To address consumer engagement and energy literacy (related to WP6), interactive activities and educational initiatives will be designed and developed. Energy scheduling should be optimised to maximise self-consumption. The opportunity to adopt new financial and regulatory models will also be addressed.
LL5	Participants in the Greek LL are typically engaged in controlling their heating systems and monitoring energy consumption through either manual or remote methods (using a thermostat or the mobile application). LL5 focuses on enhancing user engagement through the DOMX mobile application, which will offer features to involve end users in decision-making processes throughout the project. Currently, user engagement is low, and the ultimate goal is to update the application to make it more user-friendly and appealing. Additionally, new techniques will be implemented to encourage more consistent use.
LL6	The lab is a demonstration testbed with no permanent or temporary residence. In that case, end-user engagement is not applicable.

Energy Assets

Table 9 summarises the main energy assets installed and operational across the project's LLs (LL1-LL6). Each LL represents a distinct experimental environment where innovative solutions for energy generation, conversion, storage, and management are being tested, together with advanced approaches for flexibility and demand response. For each site, the table provides information on the energy vectors involved, the technologies deployed, the scale of implementation, and the user interaction mechanisms. It also highlights operational remarks and planned developments, including ongoing integrations and challenges encountered during deployment. This overview enables a systematic comparison of the different technological configurations and management models adopted in the LLs, providing a common basis for analysing interoperability, scalability, and user engagement within the EU-DREAM project.

Table 9 – Energy Assets in LLs.

LL1 Energy Assets				
Energy Vectors: Electricity				
Category	Description/Technology	Deployment Size	User Interaction	Notes / Remarks
Energy Generation	PV	9 houses, ~3 kWp each	Mobile app: real-time monitoring of production	Expansion planned during the project
Energy Conversion	Electric heaters, Electric water heaters	Select homes	Remote ON/OFF through smart plugs, scheduling via app	Proof-of-concept for space/water heating; Not the main focus
	HVAC	Select homes	Temperature and fan control via app	N/A

Energy Storage	BESS	3 houses equipped with 3 BESS from different brands: TAB (9.6 kWh), Meterboost (2.4 kWh), PylonTech (3.5 kWh)	Remote control for 9.6 kWh	Expansion for control planned
	EV Charger	6 houses: ABB (1), i-charging (4), EmonEVSE (1)	Charging/discharging control planned	Integration with EMS is under development
EMS	Cloogy Hub	Houses with smart plugs	Mobile app	Basic plug control, data collection
	Kiub	Houses with advanced control	Mobile app	BESS management, enhanced processing, and data collection
Flexibility & DR	Aggregated BESS for ancillary services	Community-scale potential	N/A	N/A

LL2 Energy Assets

Energy Vectors: Electric, Thermal (Heating, Cooling, Domestic Hot Water)

Category	Description/Technology	Deployment Size	User Interaction	Notes / Remarks
Energy Generation	PV (BIPV, BAPV, PVT), Thermal Solar Panels,	Characteristics such as size (m ²) and capacity (kW) detailed in Tables 1 & 2 (Annex A).	Currently, inhabitants have only thermostat control.	Planned dashboard/app to provide measurement results and capture feedback.
Energy Conversion	Heat pumps (AW/WW), individual (1 per house) or collective (1 per 2-4 houses) Electric Boiler	Efficiency and sizing are detailed in Tables 1 & 2 (Annex A).	Manual thermostat control per room.	Dashboard/app planned for feedback and measurement visualisation.
Energy Storage	BESS; Thermal storage	Sizes, efficiency, charge/discharge times detailed in Tables 1 & 2 (Annex A).	No direct user control currently.	Dashboard/app planned for monitoring and feedback
EMS	SmarThor data platform	Control signals for heating optimisation, self-consumption of solar energy, and	User currently has no access beyond thermostat control.	Planned dashboard/app for data visualisation and feedback

		flexibility exploitation.		
Flexibility & DR	Flexibility and demand response	Capabilities under development within the oPEN Lab project.	N/A	Under development
LL3 Energy Assets				
Energy Vectors: Electric, Thermal (Heating/Cooling/Domestic Hot water)				
Category	Description/Technology	Deployment Size	User Interaction	Notes / Remarks
Energy Generation	PV (to be verified)	Laboratory: dedicated PV system for real-time data acquisition in residential homes.	Laboratory: manual, remote control, digital platform. Residential: interaction mode to be defined.	The positive results, preliminary tested in the laboratory related to user interaction mechanisms, will be subsequently tested in 1-2 residential homes with real users.
EMS	EU-DREAM WP2 & WP3 solutions: Digital Twin and Data Management Infrastructure	No dedicated EMS installed for monitoring and optimisation; leveraging existing EU-DREAM solutions.	Various WP4 solutions will be tested for user interaction and control in residential LL.	Focus on demand response management of energy loads; solutions to be tested in Italian LL.
Flexibility & DR	Remote control of appliances	Laboratory and residential LL3: IoT Aggregator enables remote control capabilities	Laboratory: remote control mechanisms via digital platform. Residential: same, under testing for feasibility and user acceptability. (Planned)	Enabling factors include IoT infrastructure and digital platforms. Specific applications to residential appliances will be tested.
LL4 Energy Assets				
Energy Vectors: Electric, Thermal				
Category	Description/Technology	Deployment Size	User Interaction	Notes / Remarks
Energy Generation	PV	Size and rated power vary across households: 4 kWp – 6 kWp	Users interact via Natural Language Model (NLM); AI interprets requests into control commands	N/A

Energy Conversion	Heat Pump	Rated power varies across households: 7 kW	Users interact via NLM; AI interprets commands to control heating	N/A
Energy Storage	BESS	5 kWh	Users interact via NLM; AI interprets commands to manage storage	N/A
EMS	DCSix Wattrics	N/A	N/A	N/A
Flexibility & DR	IoT platform	N/A	N/A	The IoT platform takes tariff data as input to the model
LL5 Energy Assets				
Energy Vectors: Electric, Thermal				
Category	Description/Technology	Deployment Size	User Interaction	Notes / Remarks
Energy Generation	PV	One household equipped with a PV generator	Users interact via the DomX app to monitor PV generation and consumption	N/A
Energy Conversion	Heat Pumps, Gas Boilers	Heat pumps: 8.6 – 26 kW for heating/cooling and hot water; Gas boilers: 18 – 38 kW in LL5	Users can interact manually via the DOMX thermostat or remotely via the DOMX mobile app.	
Energy Storage	BESS	One household equipped with 10.24 kWh BESS	Monitoring possible via PV inverter management application; no direct control.	
EMS	EMS with mobile app and web dashboard	Installed for data monitoring and control	Users interact through a mobile app; building managers use a web dashboard	
Flexibility & DR	N/A	N/A	N/A	Flexibility potential and Demand control (for energy suppliers) and dynamic pricing consumption optimisation (for end-users) will be tested.
LL6 Energy Assets				
Energy Vectors: Electric, Thermal (Hot Water Heating)				

Category	Description/Technology	Deployment Size	User Interaction	Notes / Remarks
Energy Generation	Roof-top PV; Wind Turbine	PV: 10 kW (two fixed & tilted rows) Wind turbine: 5 kW, grid-following, yaw-capable, cut-in/out: 5–20 m/s	Fully integrated into centralised IoT infrastructure (FIWARE + LabVIEW + Grafana). Manual & remote control; real-time data acquisition. Device documentation provided.	N/A
Energy Conversion	Methanol-based Fuel Cell	5 kW	Fully integrated into a centralised IoT infrastructure.	N/A
Energy Storage	Lithium-ion BESS	5 kWh	VICTRON HMI for SoC, voltage/current, operation mode switching; Ethernet protocols; integrated into IoT platform.	N/A
EMS	Case-study-driven dynamic EMS	Configurable EMS	EMS algorithms open-source and local; user interaction depends on case study; researchers adjust EMS logic through lab interfaces.	Research-oriented environment with flexible EMS rather than a fixed system; no permanent residents.
Flexibility & DR	DR algorithm integrated into IoT architecture	Node-JS DR service prioritising loads & scheduling entities	Controlled via an IoT platform; automated DR actions applied to devices based on prioritisation logic	Links all devices, adjusts parameters based on user preferences & EMS logic

Monitoring and Control Systems

Table 10 provides an overview of the monitoring and control infrastructures implemented across the project's LLs (LL1–LL6). Each LL integrates a combination of IoT platforms, sensors, actuators, and automated control systems to enable data acquisition, system supervision, and user interaction with energy assets. The table summarises the main components and functionalities of these systems, including the IoT infrastructure and digital platforms in use, the types of sensors and actuators installed, and the presence of automated control mechanisms for optimising energy generation, storage, and consumption. It also details the data collection frequency, the availability and sharing formats of the collected datasets, and the integration capabilities with external systems and APIs. This comparative overview highlights the technological diversity among the LLs in terms of monitoring architecture, data granularity, and control strategies. It also provides insights into the maturity levels of automation and interoperability at each site, supporting the assessment of scalability, replicability, and integration potential within the EU-DREAM project.

Table 10 – Monitoring and Control Systems in LLs.

LL1	
IoT infrastructure & digital platforms	PV, BESS, EV chargers, smart meters/plugs; Kiub/Cloogy gateway; mobile app for users and web app for administrators, technicians and REC managers.
Sensors/actuators installed	Shelly meters, smart plugs, HVAC controllers, BESS, EV chargers.
Automated control systems	Automated control of BESS, EV chargers, smart-plug loads to minimise CO ₂ or cost. Inputs: consumption, PV, forecasts, load patterns.
Real-time data collection	1 to 5 minute sampling → gateway → cloud.
Data availability	Time-series (5 to 15-min), power/energy, SoC, temperature; since 2022; MB scale; shareable if anonymised; CSV/DB.
External system integration	API for data and asset control.
LL2	
IoT infrastructure & digital platforms	Cloud MS Azure (SmarThor). Data access for research/industry/public entities.
Sensors/actuators installed	>200 parameters per house are measured: temperature, RH, CO ₂ , PV, heat pump, ventilation, water use, window opening, etc.
Automated control systems	Future heating control for self-consumption optimisation and flexibility.
Real-time data collection	1-minute acquisition, hourly storage; no real-time yet.
Data availability	Data is collected on a minute-by-minute basis and stored in the SmarThor platform every hour; API & dashboard; CSV; shareable only with partners (external sharing under agreement).
External system integration	API access for authorised partners.
LL3	
IoT infrastructure & digital platforms	IoT Aggregator, Wi-Fi AP, smart relays; WiFi AP (Access Point).
Sensors/actuators installed	Power meters, HVAC via ModBus/OpenTherm, solenoid valve relay, and heat pump COP meters.
Automated control systems	Remote appliance control.
Real-time data collection	Real-time capability under validation (PV & devices).
Data availability	Appliance energy logging: format depends on sensors; sharing per IREN policies.
External system integration	Integration with vendor APIs + EU-DREAM via API/MQTT.

LL4	
IoT infrastructure & digital platforms	ESP32 + CT clamps, MQTT edge (Jetson), EU-DREAM cloud. Open-source ESPHome / Home Assistant.
Sensors/actuators installed	CT clamps for smart meter, heat pump, EV, PV, BESS.
Automated control systems	N/A
Real-time data collection	1-second resolution possible (current 60 sec). Timestamp added only.
Data availability	.txt; 1-min / 30-min; MB; NDA required; no external sharing.
External system integration	No external integration yet; future API possible.
LL5	
IoT infrastructure & digital platforms	DOMX IoT platform; WiFi-enabled Smart Heating Controller; WiFi-enabled Energy Monitoring device for electricity consumption; WiFi-enabled Indoor Air Quality sensor.
Sensors/actuators installed	Smart heating (Modbus/Opentherm), IAQ sensors, energy meters.
Automated control systems	PV & BESS automated (Fronius system with local API).
Real-time data collection	Real-time for all devices.
Data availability	DOMX LL utilises a secure, cloud-based platform to collect, store, and manage a wide range of data.
External system integration	REST APIs; forwarding services; privacy guaranteed.
LL6	
IoT infrastructure & digital platforms	IoT ecosystem including smart indoor/outdoor sensors, smart plugs/relays, smart and prosumer meters, and IoT-ready appliances (e.g., microwave and fridge), all connected through a multi-protocol sensor network. A real-time energy management and control platform enables monitoring, forecasting, and optimisation of household energy usage.
Sensors/actuators installed	Smart meters, smart plugs/cables/relays, occupancy & IAQ sensors, weather sensors.
Automated control systems	Full control of RES and loads; inputs: time, occupancy, temperature, price signals; goals: scheduling, storage optimisation, flexibility.
Real-time data collection	Near real-time via multi-protocol network.
Data availability	LL6 data include voltage, current, active/reactive power, temperature, luminance, occupancy, weather, and device status, collected in real time via smart plugs and gateways and stored as time series for

	<p>historical analysis. Measurements are mostly power consumption/generation (kW) at 5–10 second intervals, including voltage, current, power factor, room temperature, luminance, and device on/off status; data from 2018 onward, GB scale, available to project partners, in CSV/JSON formats.</p>
<p>External system integration</p>	<p>Open-source, NGSI formats: APIs can be developed on a case-by-case basis.</p>

REQUIREMENTS

Formally defining system requirements is a mandatory step in applying the UC methodology. The structured approach prescribed by the International Standard IEC 62559-2:2015 has been adopted. To ensure comprehensive coverage and consistency, all identified requirements are organised in a formal taxonomy. This categorisation segments requirements across seven distinct architectural layers, from Business to Implementation. The adopted categorisation model is detailed in Table 11.

Table 11 – Suggested list of categories from IEC 62559-2:2015.

Group	Category ID	Category Name
1 Business layer		
	1.1	Regulatory policy
	1.2	Business objectives
2 Functional layer		
	2.1	Business procedures
3 Information layer		
	3.1	Business context
	3.2	Semantic understanding
4 Communication layer		
	4.1	Syntactic interoperability
	4.2	Network interoperability
5 Component layer		
	5.1	Basic connectivity
6 Cross-cutting issues		
	6.1	Shared meaning of content
	6.2	Resource identification
	6.3	Time synchronisation and sequencing
	6.4	Logging and auditing
	6.5	Transaction and state management
	6.6	System preservation
	6.7	Quality of service
	6.8	Discovery and configuration
	6.9	System evolution and scalability
7 Implementation		
	7.1	Information system and communication protection
	7.2	Data management
	7.3	Functional performance requirements
	7.4	Safety and risk assessment
	7.5	Connections and HMI (human-machine interface)

Based on the framework defined in IEC 62559-2, the EU-DREAM system requirements have been derived and grouped according to the relevant abstraction layers (Business, Functional, Information, Communication, Cross-cutting, and Implementation). The resulting set of requirements is presented in Table 12, where each entry includes a unique Requirement Identifier (R-ID), its associated category, and a concise description of the intended functionality. Some requirements are related to Platform requirements described in D1.2 System Architecture.

Table 12 – Requirements.

R-ID	Requirement Name	Category Category Name	ID Description
1: Business layer			
BUS-POL-01	Regulatory Framework Compliance	1.1 Regulatory policy	The EU-DREAM platform shall adhere to all relevant European and national regulations, including but not limited to personal data protection (e.g., GDPR), energy market rules, standards for cybersecurity and interoperability. Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-008
2: Function layer			
FUN-BP-01	User Insight Query Procedure	2.1 Business procedures	The EU-DREAM platform shall support a procedure starting from the user natural language input, proceeding through data analysis, and concluding with the presentation of a structured and appropriate response to the user's query.
FUN-BP-02	User Command Execution Procedure	2.1 Business procedures	The EU-DREAM platform shall support a procedure that begins with a user's natural language command (e.g., setting an alarm, defining a preference), translates the intent into system parameters, and confirms execution to the user.
FUN-BP-03	Demand Response Event Management	2.1 Business procedures	The EU-DREAM platform shall manage demand response events by receiving external signals, translating them into information for users (e.g. event, suggested actions, etc.), and collecting user responses or automated device actions to influence energy consumption patterns.

FUN-BP-04	User Engagement & Nudging Procedure	2.1 Business procedures	The EU-DREAM platform shall implement a procedure to provide nudges and educational content to users, aiming to promote behavioural changes towards energy efficiency and sustainability.
FUN-BP-05	Simulation and Forecasting Capabilities	2.1 Business procedures	The EU-DREAM platform shall include predictive tools capable of forecasting energy demand, production and pricing trends. These tools support stakeholders in strategic planning, operational decision-making, and proactive grid engagement. Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-003
FUN-BP-06	Real-Time Data Monitoring	2.1 Business procedures	The EU-DREAM platform shall be able to receive, manage and process real-time data, enabling users and operators to observe energy production, consumption, and flexibility indicators. Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-005
FUN-BP-07	Energy Flexibility Management Services	2.1 Business procedures	The EU-DREAM platform shall deliver functionalities that enable energy flexibility management, such as automated demand response, load shifting, and the coordination of distributed energy resources. Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-006
3: Information layer			
INF-SEM-01	Common Data Model Adherence	3.2 Semantic understanding	All data exchanged within and between EU-DREAM platform components and connected LLs shall adhere to a predefined common semantic model to ensure the unambiguous meaning of terms (e.g., "consumption", "cost", "production") across different systems involved (e.g., Optimiser, NLP, etc.).
4: Communication layer			
COM-SYN-01	Platform Data Interoperability	4.1 Syntactic interoperability	The EU-DREAM platform shall support interoperability with heterogeneous

			<p>data sources, including legacy systems, IoT devices, building management systems, weather forecasts and smart meters. It shall primarily utilise open standards and APIs to enable seamless data exchange and integration with both internal and third-party components.</p> <p>Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-002</p>
COM-SYN-02	Data Exchange with External Data Sources	4.1 Syntactic interoperability	The EU-DREAM platform shall be able to interface via APIs to acquire structured external data, such as weather forecasts, price signals (Day-Ahead), etc.
COM-SYN-03	Grid Exchange Interoperability	4.1 Syntactic interoperability	The EU-DREAM platform shall support interfaces for bi-directional exchange with the utility grid (or its simulation) for energy marketing purposes, where permitted by regulation and available technical interfaces, enabling control and measurement of energy exchange.
COM-SYN-04	Market Platform Integration	4.1 Syntactic interoperability	<p>The EU-DREAM platform shall support integration with external energy markets, local flexibility markets, or aggregators' platforms.</p> <p>Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-007</p>
6: Cross-cutting issues			
QOS-RT-01	Real-Time Data Processing	6.7 Quality of service	The platform's architecture shall be designed to support time-sensitive functionalities (e.g., optimisation, price notifications), aiming to minimise latency for the timely delivery of information and commands.
QOS-UI-01	User Interface Responsiveness	6.7 Quality of service	The EU-DREAM platform's user interface shall be designed to provide a fluid and intuitive user experience. The design must adhere to established usability principles, ensuring that users receive timely feedback for their actions and that the interface remains responsive during data loading and processing operations.

QOS-RELI-01	Data Accuracy and Reliability	6.7 Quality of service	The EU-DREAM platform shall implement mechanisms to ensure the accuracy and reliability of collected energy data, forecasts, and optimisation outputs to support informed user decisions and system operations.
QOS-SCL-01	Architectural Scalability	6.9 System evolution and scalability	The EU-DREAM system architecture shall be modular and designed to allow for future expansion and adaptation. This includes the integration of additional services, tools, or pilot cases without disrupting existing functionality. Scalability shall support replication across different geographic locations, user types, and energy systems. Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-001
7: Implementation			
IMP-SEC-01	Secure Communication Channels	7.1 Information system and communication protection	All network communications carrying user data or control commands within the EU-DREAM platform shall ensure encryption and secure transport protocols (e.g. TLS or equivalent).
IMP-SEC-02	Data Privacy and User Control	7.1 Information system and communication protection	The EU-DREAM platform shall implement mechanisms to ensure data privacy and provide users with explicit control over how their energy consumption and personal data are accessed and shared, in compliance with regulations like GDPR.
IMP-SEC-03	Role-Based Access Control	7.1 Information system and communication protection	The EU-DREAM platform shall implement a secure access management framework that provides differentiated rights and permissions based on the user. Linked to Platform Requirement: R1-004
IMP-FP-01	NLP Intent Recognition	7.3 Functional performance requirements	The platform shall include a Natural Language Processing (NLP) module capable of identifying user intents (e.g., queries, commands, preferences) from unstructured text.

IMP-FP-02	Optimisation Algorithm Execution	7.3 Functional performance requirements	The EU-DREAM platform shall be capable of executing optimisation algorithms to optimise consumption/charging plans with respect to an objective (e.g., cost or emissions), subject to configured constraints (user preferences, device status).
IMP-FP-03	Alarm Condition Evaluation	7.3 Functional performance requirements	The EU-DREAM platform shall periodically or event-driven evaluate user-defined alarm conditions (e.g., consumption thresholds, price) and generate a notification when a condition is met.
IMP-FP-04	User Preferences Configuration	7.3 Functional performance requirements	The EU-DREAM platform shall enable users to define and modify their energy preferences (e.g., EV charging targets, energy source priorities) via the user interface, which will then be translated into configuration parameters for the energy management system.

BUSINESS OBJECTIVES

The EU-DREAM Business Plan defines the project's global commercial strategy by analysing the entire value chain and identifying market opportunities for the technological solutions generated. It adopts a modular, flexible business architecture, allowing each subsystem to be used as a stand-alone product or as an integrated service. The plan focuses on translating project results into viable business opportunities for industrial partners through targeted market studies, technology transfer, and tailored exploitation strategies. Overall, it ensures that EU-DREAM's products and services form a sustainable, competitive ecosystem ready for market entry.

In Table 13, the Business Objectives (BO1–BO4) outline the key directions guiding this exploitation strategy.

Table 13 – Business Objectives as defined in the Grant Agreement.

BO	Description
BO1	Follow a platform-based, multi-sided, consumer-centric business modelling approach, considering a design thinking approach and user empathy. The software infrastructure/platform should be accessed by multiple types of users via the Internet and be available on any type of device.
BO2	Enable AI-powered and NLP-based tools to support the exponential growth of digital technologies for the end-users. The technical design should be based on the latest advancements in web-based services' engineering, allowing the platform to scale up efficiently.
BO3	Foster open ecosystems with a focus on APIs, enabling open, combinatorial and incremental innovation. Each interested consumer can select among several combinations of functional components that best fit its targeted business needs. Also, the modules should be easily extended according to the future end-users and the system's requirements.
BO4	Reflect on the most recent and expected future trends in both technological and societal developments, the ones related to digital technologies and consumer preferences. The product portfolio should follow a well-designed mixture of emerging technological and societal developments.

USE CASES

Methodology

Preliminary Use Case Collection

Upon completion of the LL characterisation phase, a comprehensive methodology for UC identification and description was established. This methodology was used to ensure systematic and harmonised contributions from all consortium partners. The entire process was aligned with both project-specific objectives and broader European energy transition priorities, while maintaining consistency with established international standard IEC 62559-2:2015 (IEC, 2015). The initial step involved the dissemination of a preliminary UC documentation template to all LL Responsible Partners. This template was designed to capture multiple dimensions of each proposed UC, ensuring strategic alignment with the project's goals and European policy frameworks. Key elements captured in this preliminary template included:

- Time Frame classification: Categorising UCs according to their operational horizon (e.g., Planning, Day Ahead, Real Time operations)
- Use Case Categories: Defining the primary purpose and scope (e.g., planning-oriented, operational, optimisation-focused)
- Description and Objectives: Providing a comprehensive overview of the UC, with particular emphasis on alignment with pan-European energy targets and customer engagement enhancement strategies
- Actor Identification and Interaction Mapping: Defining all stakeholders involved and their respective roles and interactions within the UC
- Preliminary Feasibility Assessment: Analysis of the technical and organisational readiness of each LL, identifying potential gaps, barriers, and initial requirements
- Replicability and Scalability Potential: Evaluating the transferability of the UC to other contexts and its potential for broader deployment

Each LL Responsible Partner was requested to propose a minimum of three potential UCs applicable to their specific LL context. Partners were instructed to complete the preliminary template thoroughly, ensuring that all dimensions were adequately addressed and that the proposed UCs reflected both local specificities and project-wide strategic objectives. A comprehensive review phase was conducted to harmonise and refine the preliminary UC descriptions submitted by the partners. This iterative process involved critical assessment of the proposed UCs, identification of inconsistencies or gaps, and provision of constructive feedback to enhance clarity, completeness, and alignment with project requirements and the capability of the LL. The review process ensured methodological consistency across all LLs.

Detailed Use Case Description

To ensure the transition from preliminary concepts to technically robust and formalised descriptions, a detailed template was developed and adopted, leveraging IEC 62559-2:2015 (IEC, 2015). This internationally recognised framework ensures technical rigour and provides a common language essential for subsequent modelling, analysis, and standardisation activities. The detailed template, along with compilation examples, was circulated to ensure a consistent understanding of terminology and vocabulary across the consortium (in particular, we have followed the definitions in Table 14 extracted from IEC 62559-2:2015).

Table 14 - Definition of the terms (IEC, 2015).

Term	Description
Use Case	Specification of a set of actions performed by a system, which yields an observable result that is, typically, of value for one or more actors or other stakeholders of the system.
Actor	An entity that communicates and interacts. These actors can include people, software applications, systems, databases, and even the power system itself.
System	A set of interrelated elements considered in a defined context as a whole and separated from their environment. A system is generally defined with the view of achieving a given objective, for example, by performing a definite function.
Scenario	A possible sequence of interaction
Activity Step	An elementary step within a scenario representing the finest-grained description level of interactions in the UC.

The structure of the Detailed Use Case Template used for documenting each UC is detailed as follows, mirroring the organisational structure described in the IEC standard:

Detailed Use Case Template

The structure of the Detailed Use Case template used for documenting each UC is detailed as follows:

- **Use Case Identification:** This subsection provides key details for identification.
 - *ID:* A unique identifier of UC used within the project
 - *Name of Use Case:* A short name referring to the use case's activity
 - *Category(ies):* Indicate the main purposes of the UC (e.g. Operational, Economic, Environmental, Social, etc.)
- **Version management:** This section tracks the lifecycle of the document, including Version Number, Date, Name of Author(s), Changes made and Status.
- **Scope and Objectives of Use Case:** This subsection describes the motivation and context of the UC
 - *Scope:* it describes the aims and boundaries of the UC in short form
 - *Objectives:* a list of the goals the UC aims to achieve
 - *Related business case(s):* a list of Business Objectives involved
- **Narrative of Use Case:** This is the descriptive core of the UC from a user's perspective
 - *Short description:* A brief overview of the UC
 - *Complete description:* A comprehensive, longer narrative from the user's viewpoint about what happens and under which assumptions. It can be understood by non-experts as well.
- **Key Performance Indicator (KPI):** This section specifies the performance indicators related to the UC
 - *ID:* A unique identifier that allows the unambiguous reference of each KPI within and across Use Cases of the same LL.
 - *Name:* Short name that identifies the KPI
 - *Description:* Description of KPI
 - *Reference to the mentioned use case objectives:* List of Objectives related to the KPI
- **Use Case conditions:** This section defines the assumptions for the UC
 - *Assumptions:* General presumptions about conditions or system configurations.

- *Prerequisites*: Requirements that must be met for the basis scenario UC to be successfully accomplished.
- **Further Information on the Use Case for Classification/Mapping**: This section helps categorise and relate the UC to others
 - *Relation to other use cases*: Specifies known relations to other UCs.
 - *Level of depth*: The level of depth reflects the degree of specialisation of the UC.
 - *Prioritisation*: It ranks the UC (e.g., obligatory/mandatory, optional, nice to have, etc.)
 - *Generic, regional, or national relation*: Often UCs are applied to areas where restrictions by law or similar issues occur, so for generalisation the generic, regional or national relation has to be specified.
 - *Nature of the use case*: The nature of the use case describes the viewpoint and field of attention, such as technical, political, business/market, test, process, etc.
 - *Further keywords for classification*: Other keywords that can be used to classify the considered UC
- **General Remarks**: Any number of general remarks which do not fit in any other category
- **Diagram of Use Case**
 - *System Architecture*: indicating the components in the System Architecture (as defined in D1.2) that will be involved in the UC.
 - *Use Case Diagram*: it shows the system's main functionalities, the actors involved and the interaction between them. For the social and co-creation Use Cases, a Conceptual Overview diagram was used, as it more appropriately represents the interactions between participants, organisers, and other stakeholders involved in the co-creation sessions.
 - *Sequence Diagram*: it illustrates the temporal order of interactions between actors and the system, showing which messages are exchanged, between whom and in what sequence. It offers a dynamic view of scenarios related to the UC, detailing step by step the flow of communication between actors and the system.
- **Technical Details**
 - *Actors*: List of all actors involved in the UC. For each actor, the Name, the Actor Type (e.g. Device, System, Human), the Description and Further information specific to the considered UC.
 - *References*: List of all References used to compile the UC
- **Step-by-Step Analysis of Use Case**
 - *Overview of Scenarios*: List of all considered scenarios for the UC. For each Scenario is provided the *ID*, the *Scenario Name*, the *Scenario Description*, the *Primary Actor* (the actor(s) that trigger(s) the scenario), the *Triggering Event* (event(s) trigger(s) the scenario), the *Pre-condition* (condition(s) should have met before the scenario happens), *Post-condition* (condition(s) should prevail after the scenario happens).
 - *Steps – Scenarios*: Each step describes a part of a communication or action depicted in the Sequence Diagram. The steps of the scenario are listed in consecutive execution order, with each step's number and the triggering event (the event that triggers the step). Each step represents a process or activity which gets a unique name and a brief explanation of the procedure. The second part

deals with the information exchanged at each step. The *Service* represents the nature of the information flow with the following possibilities:

- GET (default): The Receiver requests information from the Producer.
 - CREATE: The information Producer creates an information object.
 - CHANGE: Producer updates the Receiver's information
 - DELETE: Producer deletes information from the Receiver
 - CANCEL/CLOSE: A process is terminated.
 - EXECUTE: An action or service is performed.
 - REPORT: Producer provides information to the Receiver.
 - TIMER: Waiting period. The information Producer and Receiver have to be the same actor.
 - REPEAT: A number of steps has to be repeated until a break condition (stated in the field Event) is satisfied. The contemplated steps have to be added in parentheses.
- The *Information Producer* and the *Information Receiver* are both actors from the actor list described previously. Each step is related to one or more *Information Exchanged* and to one or more *Requirements*.
- **Information Exchanged:** List all information exchanged in all considered scenarios for the UC. For each Information Exchanged, the *Name*, the *Description* and the linked *Requirement ID*.
 - **Common Terms and Definitions:** List of all definitions, common terms, and acronyms used in the UC.

Baselines / Needs / Gaps

For each UC, the baselines, gaps and needs are presented together as a concise indication of the LL's current ability to support the proposed functionality and of the conditions required to make its implementation feasible. This integrated description reflects and synthesises the more detailed information already provided in the LLs' Characteristics section and in Annex A, highlighting only the specific elements that are directly relevant to the UC.

Overview of proposed Use Cases

Each UC has been selected to reflect one or more of the project's principal dimensions: from data-driven decision support and AI-based management of energy flows to intuitive user interaction, behavioural change mechanisms, and stakeholder-led co-creation processes.

To structure this diversity coherently, the UCs are organised into five general categories:

- **Optimisation & Control:** These UCs focus on the automation, orchestration, and intelligent control of energy assets, to reduce costs and/or the carbon footprint while preserving occupant comfort.
- **Insights & Awareness:** This category empowers users with meaningful and actionable information about their consumption, generation, and environmental impact, often through dashboards or natural-language interfaces, thus improving energy literacy, transparency and informed decision-making.
- **Preferences & Configuration:** These UCs emphasise intuitive ways for users to set comfort, cost or sustainability preferences, and configure operational parameters without technical burden.

- **Alerts, Education & Nudging:** The UCs in this category provide real-time alerts, contextual feedback and behavioural prompts designed to stimulate sustained engagement and trigger more efficient energy habits.
- **Co-Creation & Social Innovation:** These UCs involve residents, housing companies, maintenance providers and communities in participatory design, co-creation workshops and community energy initiatives, ensuring solutions are aligned with real needs and socially acceptable.

The list of proposed UCs and their main belonging category is presented in Table 15.

Table 15 – List of proposed UCs grouped by LLs and its main belonging category

LL	UC	Main Category
LL1	LL1_UC1 – Energy/Economic/Environmental Insights using NLP	Insights & Awareness
	LL1_UC2 – Set Alerts and Notifications using NLP	Alerts, Education & Nudging
	LL1_UC3 – Define Optimisation Settings using NLP	Preferences & Configuration
	LL1_UC4 – Optimise Energy Flows to Reduce Cost	Optimisation & Control
	LL1_UC5 – Energy Insights for REC Members using NLP	Insights & Awareness
LL2	LL2_UC1 – Collaborative Design of Interface for SHC	Co-Creation & Social Innovation
	LL2_UC2 – Co-Creation on Digital Tools for Energy Literacy	Co-Creation & Social Innovation
	LL2_UC3 – Behaviour Change for Energy Efficiency	Co-Creation & Social Innovation
LL3	LL3_UC1 – Energy Cost Reduction Plan	Optimisation & Control
	LL3_UC2 – Real-Time Energy Optimiser	Optimisation & Control
	LL3_UC3 – Low-Emission Energy Optimiser	Optimisation & Control
LL4	LL4_UC1 – Saving Customers Money (AI)	Optimisation & Control
	LL4_UC2 – Strengthening the Grid (of the future)	Optimisation & Control
	LL4_UC3 – NLP Complex Insights	Insights & Awareness
	LL4_UC4 – End User Education	Alerts, Education & Nudging
LL5	LL5_UC1 – Reduce Energy Consumption for Space Heating	Optimisation & Control
	LL5_UC2 – Energy Cost Optimisation	Optimisation & Control
	LL5_UC3 – NLP Complex Insights	Insights & Awareness
	LL5_UC4 – Promote Long-Term Engagement through In-App Nudging	Alerts, Education & Nudging
LL6	LL6_UC1 – DT-enabled Solutions for Smart Houses	Optimisation & Control
	LL6_UC2 – Optimisation and Strategic Management with Grid	Optimisation & Control
	LL6_UC3 – Enhanced Load Scheduling	Preferences & Configuration

LL1

LL1_UC1- Energy/Economic/Environmental Insights using NLP

Scope of Use Case

Enable users to obtain real-time and historical energy-related insights (e.g., consumption, cost, generation) using natural language to interact with the EMS system.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Enhance user awareness and decision-making**
Provide meaningful insights to help users optimise energy usage, reduce costs, and improve efficiency.
- **Obj2: Promote proactive energy management**
Encourage users to monitor their energy consumption trends over time and take informed actions based on the insights provided.
- **Obj3: Facilitate seamless interaction with the EMS**
Enable intuitive, conversational interactions with EMS to ensure ease of use and user-friendliness.

Related Business Case(s)

BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC describes how end users can ask questions about their energy-related information using a natural language interface to the EMS, which analyses historical data and forecasts to provide answers to the questions.

Users living in homes equipped with an EMS can interact with the system via an NLP interface to obtain comprehensive insights into their energy consumption patterns. The EMS, using historical data or forecasts, allows questions like “How much will I pay at the end of the month?” or “Which of my appliances consumes the most energy?” to be answered in natural language. The EMS compares current usage with past data, evaluates efficiency contributions from renewable sources (e.g., solar panels), and forecasts consumption and costs.

Although EMS systems are already deployed, they currently lack intelligent querying capabilities and automated analysis, gaps that this UC aims to address.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

The LL houses already have an EMS collecting data from consumption and production. At this moment, to execute this UC, it lacks the NLP module and some adaptations to the API to simplify data analysis.

LL1_UC2 - Set Alerts and Notifications using NLP

Scope of Use Case

Enable users to create alerts, which identify anomalous energy usage patterns or system malfunctions, using natural language interaction with the EMS system.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Enhance energy management through intelligent alerts**
Enable users to set personalised notifications.
- **Obj2: Promote proactive energy management**
Encourage users to monitor their energy consumption trends over time and take informed actions based on the insights provided.
- **Obj3: Facilitate seamless interaction with the EMS**
Enable intuitive, conversational interactions with EMS to ensure ease of use and user-friendliness.

Related Business Case(s)

BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC describes how end users can create alerts related to anomalous energy usage patterns or low generation forecasts using a natural language interface to the EMS, which includes alert management functionality.

Users living in homes equipped with an EMS can interact with the system via an NLP interface to set alerts that notify them of abnormal energy consumption patterns. The EMS can manage alerts based on historical data or forecasts, which can be set using sentences like “Notify me if the energy consumption is significantly higher than usual” or “Notify me if the solar generation is lower than forecasted”. The EMS uses processed NLP data to set the alert with the appropriate parameters.

Although EMS systems are already deployed and manage alerts, they could benefit from easier alert-setting configuration.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

LL1 already has the EMS alarm module and collected energy data. At this moment, to execute this UC, it lacks the NLP module and some API adaptations to simplify the definition of alarms.

LL1_UC3 - Define Optimisation Settings using NLP

Scope of Use Case

Enable users to set up operational optimisation parameters using natural language to interact with the EMS system.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Enable intuitive and user-friendly preference input**
Allow users to set operational parameters using natural language commands, removing the need for tedious manual configurations.
- **Obj2: Improve user engagement and customisation**
Allow users to review and adjust their saved preferences via a user-friendly interface.
- **Obj3: Facilitate seamless interaction with the EMS**
Enable intuitive, conversational interactions with EMS to ensure ease of use and user-friendliness.

Related Business Case(s)

BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC describes how end users can configure some optimisation parameters using a natural language interface to the EMS.

Users living in homes equipped with an EMS can interact with the system via an NLP interface to set the optimisation parameters. The EMS includes an optimisation algorithm that can command certain controllable assets such as an ESS or an EV charger. The settings can be set using sentences like "Use my battery to reduce the cost" or "Charge my EV to 80% by 6 a.m." The EMS uses the processed NLP data to define the optimisation settings.

Since some of these operational parameters may need regular (daily) updates (e. g., the state of charge of the EV at a given time), the interaction with the end user should be as easy as possible.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

LL1 already has the EMS, but to execute this UC, it lacks the NLP module and some API adaptations to enable the definition of the optimisation parameters.

LL1_UC4 - Optimise Energy Flows to Reduce Cost

Scope of Use Case

Use the AI-based Optimiser module of the EMS to control the installed energy assets (e.g., ESS and EV charger) to optimise the energy flows using the user preferences.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Optimise energy flows**
Automatically adjust energy usage (load scheduling) based on electricity prices and renewable energy availability to reduce cost.
- **Obj2: Enable user-driven energy optimisation based on personalised preferences**
Allow users to define customised energy usage preferences (e.g., cost limits, sustainability goals, or peak-hour avoidance) while ensuring optimal performance and comfort.
- **Obj3: Support appliance scheduling**
Allow controllable loads to be scheduled in accordance with user preferences.

Related Business Case(s)

BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC describes how the Optimiser Module of the EMS should be able to reduce the total cost by maximising the use of renewable (self-generated) energy and load scheduling based on tariff prices.

When the EMS includes controllable assets like an ESS or an EV charger that the Optimiser Module can use, it should be possible to change a set of operational parameters that define the behaviour of the optimisation algorithm. These operational parameters may be updated regularly (e.g., the state of charge of the EV at a certain time).

The operation of the algorithm must have a well-defined set of priorities in order to guarantee that certain tasks have preference over others.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

In LL1, Open Charge Point Interface (OCPI) integration is already in place, enabling high-level data exchange with EV chargers via a Central Management System, while the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP), enabling enhanced control and actuation via a direct connection with the EV chargers, is currently under development. Integration of some BESS assets is also advanced. However, an optimisation module at the gateway level is still missing.

LL1_UC5 - Energy/Economical/Environmental Insights for REC Members using NLP

Scope of Use Case

Enable users who are members of a REC to obtain energy flow insights (e.g., contribution, saving) using natural language to interact with the EMS system.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Enhance user awareness and decision-making**
Provide meaningful insights to improve the user awareness of his/her role in the ecological transition.
- **Obj2: Strengthen engagement in RECs**
Encourage active and continuous participation by making individual contributions visible and valued, reinforcing a sense of belonging and discouraging disengagement from the community.
- **Obj3: Support EU renewable and community energy goals**
Align with EU directives on citizen participation in energy markets. Empower communities to monitor and optimise self-consumption, improving local grid efficiency.
- **Obj4: Facilitate seamless interaction with the EMS**
Enable intuitive, conversational interactions with EMS to ensure ease of use and user-friendliness.

Related Business Case(s)

BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC describes how end users who are members of a REC can ask questions about their individual participation using a natural language interface to the EMS, which calculates the energy flows.

Users, who are members of a REC, living in homes equipped with EMS can interact with the system via an NLP interface to obtain comprehensive insights into their participation in the community. The EMS, using energy flow data or forecasts, allows questions like “How much did I save this month for being a member?” or “What was my contribution to the community last month?” to be answered in natural language. The EMS calculate the energy flows between the community and each member, assigning a cost based on the established contract.

The ability to get this information in an easy-to-understand manner will foster the growth of RECs and reduce the number of members who want to leave because they do not see any benefit.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

Cleanwatts' LL system already has community energy flows calculation functionality. It needs to have an NLP module and an API adaptation to simplify the interpretation of the energy data.

LL2

LL2_UC1 - Collaborative design of an interface for social housing company (SHC) building stock management

Scope of Use Case

Organise a co-creation session with the social housing company (SHC) and maintenance parties on the design of a shared user interface, aiming to optimise the performance assessment and maintenance of their building stock, and the interactions with inhabitants.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Gather preference information on how to co-design a shared user interface accessible to the SHC, maintenance providers, and inhabitants.
- **Obj2:** Improve collaboration between the SHC and maintenance providers, aligned with current processes and practices.
- **Obj3:** Gain insights into the current practice of maintenance, and which data insights could improve this.
- **Obj4:** Gain insight into the current practice of inhabitant interaction, i.e. how technical failures are reported, appointments made, etc., and which features on the user interface could improve this.
- **Obj5:** Capture input of the co-creation session in a draft design of the user interface.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC seeks to enhance HVAC system performance in rental dwellings by leveraging measurement data to optimise maintenance practices for SHC, by means of a co-creation session.

The purpose of this UC is to establish a connection between optimising maintenance processes and the mitigation of tenants' concerns. Its primary objective is to capture input for the design of a shared user interface accessible to the social housing company (SHC), the maintenance provider, and the inhabitants. The user interface is driven by two main goals: (1) improving the technological performance of HVAC systems in rental dwellings through the systematic use of measurement data as an interaction medium, and (2) effectively integrating inhabitant notifications into the maintenance process. Within the framework of co-creation sessions, various questions will be identified and examined, with particular attention to current maintenance practices, the extent to which additional data-driven insights may enhance them, and how these improvements can also address inhabitants' concerns.

One example is the ventilation system's performance. When filters become heavily saturated, energy consumption increases while system efficiency decreases. As a result, occupants may experience reduced indoor comfort. By monitoring several measurement parameters, the maintenance team can be alerted when filters are nearing saturation, allowing timely cleaning. This proactive approach prevents performance loss, reduces energy use, and improves both system efficiency and occupant comfort.

Improvement of interaction with tenants also positively affects maintenance practices. Current practice is that inhabitants report a technical failure by phone, which often leads to frustrations:

the call service is not available 24/7, tenants call the wrong number, there is no feedback after the failure is reported, etc. If technical failures could be reported on a user interface, a more transparent communication would be possible, with e.g. automated feedback (generated with AI techniques), an online calendar where people can book a timeslot for interventions, after reporting the current status of the notification (comparable to the delivery status of a parcel)

While the purpose of the user interface is clear, the co-creation workshop is necessary to:

- Align technical optimisation with real-world needs. Optimisation should reflect actual priorities (e.g. comfort over energy efficiency), not only supporting operational efficiency but also social objectives (transparency, trust, etc.)
- Clarifying roles and collaboration: a shared user interface requires clear responsibilities among SHC, maintenance providers, and tenants. Feedback is essential to map workflows, identify communication gaps, and align incentives, ensuring data-driven insights translate into coordinated action rather than confusion.
- Identifying practical barriers and opportunities: maintenance staff can highlight constraints in current practices (e.g. scheduling, budget, etc.) that pure data analysis might overlook. Tenants' feedback might surface other hidden pain points (e.g. slow response times, etc.)
- Building trust and acceptance: By making data accessible, the risk of frustrations and miscommunication is decreased, leading to mutual trust and acceptance.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

A lot of monitoring data has already been gathered. We want to provide the SHC with insights into technical performance and failures of their HVAC systems, enabling them to plan maintenance proactively. For this use case to succeed, we need the participants' active involvement in the co-creation session.

LL2_UC2 - Co-Creation Session on Digital Tools for Resident Energy Literacy

Scope of Use Case

Organise a co-creation session with residents to explore how digital tools (including user interfaces) can be used to improve their energy literacy and to increase understanding of the energy performance of their dwellings. Using the Appreciative Inquiry method, input will be gathered on the design of a user interface: accessibility, available information, data visualisation methods, etc.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Understand what information residents need to improve energy literacy.
- **Obj2:** Engage users through an appreciative, participatory process.
- **Obj3:** Identify barriers and triggers to why people want to use digital tools or not.
- **Obj4:** Identify which communication media (newsletter, mail...) could be used complementary to digital tools and for which target groups.
- **Obj5:** Design user interface features that reflect user needs and foster social energy consciousness and autonomy

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

The co-creation session with residents will help shape user interfaces that inform them about their household's energy performance and usage. Using Appreciative Inquiry, the session will focus on harvesting input from the residents.

This UC is developed in the context of social and educational empowerment of residential energy users. During these sessions, residents will explore, discuss, and co-design the types of energy information that should be provided and how. The idea is to develop a conceptual design for a digital user interface, with other forms of interaction (such as newsletters or info sessions) possible in parallel. These alternative forms are also important to include people with low digital literacy, people with limited means (no internet connection or smartphone), people who do not want to share their data, etc. ICT experts participate to understand technical requirements, while the Organiser and the SHC facilitate logistics and engagement. The main objective is to identify which parameters are most relevant to residents for understanding the energy efficiency of their homes, and to encourage them to enhance their energy awareness through the use of digital tools.

The user interface that will be designed aims to empower inhabitants so that they have the confidence to make their own decisions regarding energy efficiency behaviour. Two examples can illustrate this: (1) Clear insight into their energy use via the user interface can give people insights to change the prepayments for energy use themselves, rather than following the suggestions of energy suppliers blindly. Energy suppliers do not know about changes such as renovation measures or a change in the number of inhabitants, which can have a huge impact on energy use and bills. (2) Clear insight into the real-time electricity uses and production by PV can support people to change their behaviour to increase self-consumption rates of solar energy. Therefore, a user interface that makes energy data accessible supports people in the energy transition, thereby increasing trust in data and digital tools.

The session is conducted using Appreciative Inquiry, a strengths-based methodology that focuses on positive dialogue rather than problem-solving. Through appreciative questioning, residents are encouraged to share their existing strengths, good practices and aspirations related to energy use. This participatory process helps uncover opportunities to be built upon, rather than focusing solely on barriers. In practice, this means that discussions will be guided by questions such as ‘what already works well in your home regarding energy use?’ or ‘what kind of information would motivate you to improve your energy performance further?’ By applying Appreciative Inquiry, the process stimulates motivation, empowerment and a sense of ownership among residents, while also ensuring that their voices directly inform the dashboard design and related communication tools.

For this co-creation session, we would like every participant to bring a personal question or expectation to the session (e.g., about their energy bill or PV app). Sharing these at the start in a circle could lower the threshold for participation, help residents formulate their needs, and create a sense of collective energy.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

A lot of monitoring data has already been gathered. We want to provide the end user with insights into their energy use and the energy performance of their house compared to other similar buildings. For this use case to succeed, participants’ active involvement in the co-creation session is needed.

LL2_UC3 - Appreciative Inquiry Workshop on Behaviour Change for Energy Efficiency

Scope of Use Case

Organise a co-creation session with residents on how to engage, support and nudge residents to change their behaviour and habits through digital tools to improve the energy efficiency of their dwelling, using the Appreciative Inquiry method.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Understand what information residents need to trigger behaviour change, and how this differs per resident profile (e.g. single households, families...)
- **Obj2:** Engage users through a positive, participatory process.
- **Obj3:** Identify barriers and triggers to why people want to change their behaviour or not.
- **Obj4:** Elaborate on the design of the user interface developed in LL2_UC2, aiming to trigger a change in behaviour
- **Obj5:** Educate people on how to change their energy behaviour and trigger them to take action.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC engages residents to identify effective nudging strategies, understand behavioural drivers, refine the user interface, and promote energy-efficient habits through a positive, participatory process.

This UC is developed in the context of social and educational empowerment of residential energy users. During these sessions, residents will explore, discuss, and co-design the types of energy information that should be provided and how. The idea is to develop a conceptual design of a digital user interface, although other forms of interaction are also possible (e.g., newsletters or info sessions).

The session uses Appreciative Inquiry, focusing on strengths and aspirations instead of problems. The session elaborates on the input gathered in the previous co-creation session (LL2_UC2). ICT experts participate to understand technical requirements, while the Organiser and the SHC facilitate logistics and engagement. The main objective is to provide people with insights into the impact of their behaviour on energy performance and to educate them on how to change their behaviour and habits so that this positively influences the energy performance of their building. This approach aims to promote user acceptance and participation, supporting wider replicability and scalability.

Examples of nudging include real-time alerts during peak consumption, visual cues such as colours or emoticons to indicate efficient or inefficient behaviour, comparative feedback with similar households, and gamification elements that reward positive actions. The goal of nudging in this context is to encourage residents to adjust their routines while preserving freedom of choice, thereby fostering greater engagement and acceptance.

During the session, residents are encouraged not only to discuss their information needs but also to make concrete commitments for behavioural change (e.g., appliance use, thermostat settings). This ensures that the insights gained can be put into practice immediately. A follow-up check-in provides feedback on the extent to which these commitments have been realised.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

A lot of monitoring data has already been gathered. We want to provide people with insight into the impact of their behaviour on energy performance and educate them on how to change their behaviour and habits so that this positively influences the energy performance of their building. For this use case to succeed, we need the active involvement of the participants in the co-creation session.

LL3

LL3_UC1 - Energy Cost Reduction Plan

Scope of Use Case

The scope of this UC is to provide end users with tailored energy consumption plans that combine cost reduction and environmental benefits. The UC targets the planning phase, where users are supported in defining long-term strategies (weekly or monthly) to minimise costs, reduce CO₂ emissions, and improve awareness of consumption patterns.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Reduce household energy expenditure**
Provide end users with tailored weekly or monthly consumption plans to minimise electricity costs.
- **Obj2: Promote environmental sustainability**
Integrate energy and emission savings into the planning process, aligning household behaviour with EU decarbonization goals.
- **Obj3: Enhance user awareness and literacy**
Deliver transparent information on consumption patterns and cost drivers to improve user understanding and engagement.
- **Obj4: Enable autonomous execution of plans**
Allow the energy management platform to activate controllable devices according to the predefined plan, reducing manual intervention.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2

Narrative of Use Case

This UC provides households with optimised consumption plans that minimise energy costs and emissions. By analysing historical consumption, tariff schemes, and weather forecasts, the EU-DREAM platform generates tailored weekly or monthly schedules for controllable devices, helping users make informed and cost-effective decisions.

Households can lower their bills by using an intelligent planning service integrated into the EU-DREAM platform. By combining historical consumption data, tariff schemes, and weather forecasts, the system generates weekly or monthly schedules that highlight cost and emission savings. Users provide preferences via the mobile app or NLP interface, and the platform delivers clear recommendations. Plans can be approved manually or executed automatically, enabling users to benefit from optimised consumption without daily effort.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

The LL already has most of the planned remotely controllable devices installed, along with metering capabilities that enable tracking of their theoretical and actual energy consumption. However, some essential data inputs are still missing, particularly historical consumption patterns and forecast-related datasets such as weather information and day-ahead or real-time energy tariffs. To fully enable the implementation of this UC, the LL requires the availability of user-specific tariff data at the moment of consumption and the ability to test and visualise long-term (weekly/monthly) plans once the complete data pipeline is active.

LL3_UC2 - Real-Time Energy Optimiser

Scope of Use Case

This UC enables real-time cost reduction and operational efficiency by reacting to live consumption/production data and short-term forecasts (weather, PV generation, price spikes). The EU-DREAM platform detects advantageous or adverse conditions and issues actionable notifications; upon user approval (or with prior consent), it can trigger immediate control of connected assets (e.g., HVAC, smart plugs, EV charging) to shift, curtail, or schedule loads. The scope covers the real-time decision layer, user interaction (notifications/overrides), and optional automated execution.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Minimise real-time energy expenditure**
Detect and act on instant opportunities (e.g., PV surplus, off-peak windows) and risks (e.g., price spikes) to reduce costs.
- **Obj2: Enable rapid, user-centric response**
Provide notifications with clear recommendations and allow one-tap approvals or safe auto-execution with user consent.
- **Obj3: Improve operational flexibility**
Optimise controllable assets in real time (shift/curtail/charge/discharge) to balance demand with on-site generation and grid conditions.
- **Obj4: Preserve comfort, safety, and control**
Respect user preferences and constraints (comfort thresholds, device limits) and ensure transparent overrides and fail-safe behaviour.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO3

Narrative of Use Case

This UC reduces household energy costs in real time by detecting advantageous or adverse conditions from live consumption/production, tariffs, and weather forecasts, then issuing actionable notifications.

End users often miss moment-to-moment opportunities to save because prices, on-site generation, and weather change quickly. The Real-Time Energy Optimiser within the EU-DREAM platform continuously ingests live meter/asset data, short-term forecasts (weather and PV), and tariff signals to identify both **opportunities** (e.g., PV surplus, off-peak windows) and **risks** (e.g., price spikes, approaching peaks).

When a condition is detected, the user receives a clear notification with the recommended action (shift/cut/charge) and the expected **cost and CO₂ impact**. The user can approve with a single tap or enable safe **auto-execution** in advance; upon approval, the platform issues immediate commands to connected assets via the gateway, respecting device limits and user comfort constraints. All actions are logged, results are fed back to the user, and the system learns preferences over time by storing the user's choices. The solution is interoperable with heterogeneous devices and scalable across LLs, aligning real-time operational control with EU-DREAM's cost-saving and engagement objectives.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

The LL already includes remotely controllable devices and metering capabilities that allow real-time monitoring of their theoretical and actual consumption. However, some elements necessary for full implementation are not yet available, particularly the device pathway for notifying the user and receiving approval for commands, as well as historical consumption data needed to support short-term forecasting. To fully enable this UC, the LL requires the structuring of user-facing commands and preferences, ensuring the EU-DREAM App is available for interaction, and a notification system capable of engaging promptly.

LL3_UC3 - Low-Emission Energy Optimiser

Scope of Use Case

This UC aims to reduce CO₂ emissions through day-ahead energy planning that prioritises low-carbon energy sources. The EU-DREAM platform leverages forecasts of renewable production, grid carbon intensity, and user preferences to build optimal sourcing strategies. The scope includes forecast collection, optimisation, and user-facing communication of expected environmental benefits; execution may occur via automated scheduling of controllable devices or sourcing priorities.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Minimise household CO₂ footprint by aligning consumption with periods of higher renewable availability in the grid.
- **Obj2:** Ensure private renewable generation (e.g., rooftop PV) is used first whenever available.
- **Obj3:** Incorporate day-ahead forecasts of renewable generation and grid mix into consumption strategies.
- **Obj4:** Provide transparent information on carbon intensity and avoided emissions, increasing user awareness.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO3, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC minimises household CO₂ emissions by planning day-ahead energy sourcing based on forecasts of renewable generation and national grid carbon intensity. The EU-DREAM platform can prioritise self-produced renewables and align consumption with low-emission grid periods.

The Low-Emission Energy Optimiser enables households to reduce their environmental footprint by planning consumption against forecasted renewable availability and grid emission intensity. Day-ahead, the EU-DREAM platform collects renewable production forecasts (private PV/wind), grid mix forecasts, and user preferences for sustainability. It then generates an optimised sourcing plan: first using private renewable generation, then shifting flexible demand into periods where the national grid is expected to be greener. The user receives a clear summary of scheduled actions and expected CO₂ reductions. Plans can be executed automatically via controllable devices or followed manually, with results tracked against reference baselines. The approach enhances user awareness, supports the integration of renewable energy, and is replicable in any region with forecast and mix data.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

The LL already includes remotely controllable devices and the ability to monitor their theoretical consumption, which provides an initial foundation for validating day-ahead planning strategies. However, several elements needed for full implementation are still missing, including the device pathway for notifying the user and obtaining approval for commands, as well as historical consumption data required to support reliable day-ahead forecasts. To enable this UC, the LL requires the structuring of user-facing commands and day-ahead sustainability preferences, together with the availability of the EU-DREAM App for interaction and configuration.

LL4

LL4_UC1- Saving Customers Money (AI)

Scope of Use Case

This UC aims to enable consumers to save money via personalised and optimised energy suggestions generated from AI models. The AI model will make these suggestions based on the customers' energy consumption data.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Save Customers Money**
Save end-user money by shifting their consumption pattern to times when energy is cheaper.
- **Obj2: Adapt to Individual Homes**
As each home will have different equipment, the algorithm will adapt to each circumstance.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC aims to maximise self-consumption, optimise energy scheduling, and enable consumers to save money through optimised recommendations in line with their tariffs. An energy management system (EMS) will generate personalised and optimised energy suggestions tailored to customer needs based on collected energy usage data and AI models. The AI will provide recommendations on when to use or store energy, with hyperparameters adapting or updating via reinforcement learning. The customers should be able to track improvements between actual costs and optimised costs (or CO₂ emissions) to build their trust in the decision-making.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

A cloud environment is required for the effective operation of the product. Energy monitoring and DER integrations are to be installed on site using a variety of specialist equipment and API integration technologies. This will allow for baseline consumption and usage data to be captured for the "as-is" state. There is a need for NLP tools to be delivered for implementation in the cloud environment and potentially locally as well.

LL4_UC2 - Strengthening the Grid (of the future)

Scope of Use Case

This UC will test the ability of the End User to support the DSO/TSO at critical times by changing their behaviour.

Objectives

- **Obj1: Reduce Renewable Curtailment**
Shifting consumption pattern where possible, allowing for DSOs and TSOs to benefit from a 'flatter' grid demand.
- **Obj2: Increase Grid Stability**
Improve grid stability by using domestic customers as a demand side response.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC aims to maximise self-consumption and optimise energy scheduling to help support the grid.

The island of Ireland has a high level of Renewable generation (~56%). The intermittency of renewable generation, low levels of grid energy storage, and limited interconnection with other power grids are key factors that raise the importance of demand-side management and local self-consumption optimisation. AI and smart connected devices in the LLs will enable end users to maximise self-consumption and take part in simulated demand response events to support the grid. The LL homes have a blend of smart connected devices that have the potential to take part in simulated demand response events. During these simulated events, the smart connected devices will be issued requests to increase/decrease energy consumption. These devices will automatically act on consumption-based requests issued by the DSO/TSO, and the results will be measured and recorded. EU-DREAM will increase demand flexibility, optimise energy scheduling, and enable greater user compatibility (e.g., the capacity of demand-side loads to change their consumption patterns on a time scale), making the electric grid more reliable (avoid grid constraints) and increasing the usage of renewable energy sources.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

A cloud environment is required for the effective operation of the product. Energy monitoring and DER integrations are to be installed on site using a variety of specialist equipment and API integration technologies. This will allow for baseline consumption and usage data to be captured for the "as-is" state. There is a need for NLP tools to be delivered and implemented in the cloud environment, and potentially locally also.

LL4_UC3 - NLP Complex Insights

Scope of Use Case

This UC will allow the end user to interact with the EMS using natural language.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Enable natural language interfacing with EMS.
- **Obj2:** Empower with informed decision making.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

For this UC, the aim is to provide end users with an NLP interface through which they can receive real-time and historical information presented in an intuitive, user-friendly format. Historical information, real-time information, and forecasts from the AI model are all capable of providing answers to such questions. However, they previously required technical knowledge to find and further expertise to analyse. By using the NLP, however, using only natural language queries, the end user will receive comprehensive yet digestible answers. The EU-DREAM Mobile App will provide the end user with an NLP interface that will mediate their communication with the EMS. This NLP module will be able to interpret natural language queries from the user, such as *“What were my carbon emissions last month?”* *“What room in my home is using the most energy?”*, or *“What are my predicted energy expenses for the month?”* The NLP model will then translate such questions into API requests to the EU-DREAM cloud infrastructure, which will return data that informs the response that the NLP provides to the end user. This will further promote energy efficiency by empowering the end user with the means to make well-informed decisions about their energy consumption.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

A cloud environment is required for the effective operation of the product. Energy monitoring and DER integrations are to be installed on site using a variety of specialist equipment and API integration technologies. This will allow for baseline consumption and usage data to be captured for the “as-is” state. There is a need for NLP tools to be delivered and implemented in the cloud environment, and potentially locally also.

LL4_UC4 - End User Education

Scope of Use Case

For this, UC consumers will be encouraged to take a more active role in managing their energy use and production patterns.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Increase end-user understanding of their energy habits.
- **Obj2:** Promote efficient energy consumption.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC aims to have end users reflect on their relationship both with the EMS and their own energy usage habits through alerts and notifications delivered by the EU-DREAM Mobile app. Daily life is busy and has no signs of slowing down. With the growing variety of work arrangements, there is great diversity among the energy consumption habits of both homeowners and renters. Given this, it can be difficult for households to prioritise reducing their consumption habits despite the rising cost of energy.

The concept of this UC is to empower residential energy consumers through notifications from the EU-DREAM Mobile app. These notifications can be alerts set by the end user or those prompted by the EMS when behaviour in the pilot home diverges significantly from the Digital Twin. By leveraging the NLP Intermediator, we aim to simplify the process of setting these alerts as much as possible and ensure that the alerts from the EMS are easy to understand and written in natural language. Regular notifications from the EMS will grow the end user's confidence in the EU-DREAM Mobile app as well as encourage more frequent reflection on weekly and day-to-day energy habits.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

Common themes and insights will have to be documented and saved in a repository for AI and the EU-Dream app to present to the user. A knowledge base is preexisting on the app, but the content needs to be created.

LL5

LL5_UC1 - Reduce Energy Consumption for Space Heating

Scope of Use Case

This UC addresses the optimisation of residential space heating through intelligent control of natural gas boilers and heat pumps. By leveraging IoT-enabled HVAC controllers and optimisation algorithms, heating demand is dynamically adjusted to minimise energy waste while maintaining user comfort.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Support energy efficiency and decarbonization by reducing heating consumption and emissions.
- **Obj2:** Implement dynamic optimisation of heating via IoT and smart algorithms.
- **Obj3:** Enhance the integration of existing household heating systems without requiring replacements.
- **Obj4:** Adapt heating strategies to specific building thermal characteristics.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO3, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC optimises residential space heating for energy savings and emission reduction. It integrates smart HVAC controllers with optimisation algorithms to dynamically adjust heating based on occupancy, weather, and building thermal characteristics, while ensuring comfort.

Residential consumers equipped with gas boilers or heat pumps can significantly reduce their energy consumption using smart heating management. The EU-DREAM platform connects HVAC controllers, optimisers, and NLP intermediators to enable both automated optimisation and user-driven preferences.

The optimiser considers thermal characteristics of each building, occupancy patterns, and real-time weather conditions. Heating setpoints are adapted dynamically to minimise waste while preserving comfort. Consumers interact through the EU-DREAM mobile app, via natural language commands, fine-tuning heating preferences.

The system continuously learns from user behaviour and manual overrides, improving optimisation over time. This ensures scalability across different household types and replicability across EU contexts.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

A solid baseline for evaluating energy savings from smart heating control of natural gas boilers is already established. By recording consumption in baseline mode across full winter seasons and comparing days with comparable heating demand and weather conditions to periods where the energy-saving algorithm was active—over three successive winters—typical Greek households achieved average savings of approximately $\pm 30\%$

LL5_UC2 - Energy Cost Optimisation

Scope of Use Case

This UC aligns with pan-European goals of energy efficiency, carbon reduction, and grid stability. It leverages real-time electricity pricing and day-ahead signals to optimise heat pump operations. By shifting heating and hot water production to off-peak, renewable-rich periods, the system reduces consumer costs, avoids emissions, and improves grid balance. However, energy cost optimisation does not automatically ensure environmental or system benefits in every context; it highly depends on the characteristics of some markets, where low cost might coincide with high fossil-based generation, although this is not the norm. The effectiveness, therefore, **depends on the local tariff design, market signals, and generation mix.**

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Enhance energy efficiency by optimising heat pump operations.
- **Obj2:** Lower consumer energy bills by exploiting real-time and day-ahead price signals.
- **Obj3:** Reduce carbon emissions by aligning consumption with renewable generation.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO3, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC enables heat pumps to operate cost-effectively by shifting demand to off-peak, renewable-rich periods using real-time and day-ahead pricing signals.

Consumers use the DOMX smart optimiser integrated with the EU-DREAM platform to schedule heat pump operations. The optimiser monitors day-ahead pricing signals and aligns heating/hot water production with off-peak, renewable-rich periods. Preferences are provided by users through the EU-DREAM app, either via intuitive menus or natural language queries processed by the NLP mediator.

The optimisation ensures lower household bills, reduced reliance on fossil fuels, and improved integration of renewable energy into the grid, based on user preferences. Grid operators benefit from reduced peak demand, enhancing overall grid stability. Consumers retain agency, as preferences (comfort thresholds, cost-saving priorities) are incorporated into optimisation.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

In the baseline scenario, the heat pump operates in its standard mode without any smart-grid-enabled optimisation or energy-saving algorithms. Heating and hot-water production follow fixed schedules or user-defined setpoints, regardless of electricity price fluctuations or renewable availability. As a result, the system may run during high-cost or peak-demand periods, offering no cost optimisation or load-shifting benefits. The DOMX cost-optimisation algorithm for heat pumps has not yet been tested or validated under real-world conditions, leaving its performance and savings potential unquantified. To enable this UC, there is a need for integrated price-signal ingestion, robust scheduling logic, and user-friendly preference handling within the EU-DREAM platform.

LL5_UC3 - NLP Complex Insights

Scope of Use Case

This UC provides consumers with conversational, NLP-enabled access to their energy data and insights. By enabling intuitive queries through the EU-DREAM mobile app, consumers can understand patterns, costs, and optimisation opportunities in natural language.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Enable end users to interact with IoT systems via natural language.
- **Obj2:** Simplify access to energy consumption data and insights.
- **Obj3:** Promote optimisation through actionable recommendations.
- **Obj4:** Enhance engagement, accessibility, and trust in digital energy services.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO3, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

This UC allows users to access complex energy insights through natural language queries, making energy management intuitive and interactive.

Consumers often struggle to interpret raw energy data. With the EU-DREAM NLP intermediary, users interact with their IoT energy management systems via conversational queries (text or voice). The NLP module interprets these queries, accesses data from the IoT energy management backend (via APIs), and provides human-readable insights.

For example, users can ask: “What was my heating cost last week?” “Which device consumes the most energy?”, or “How much did I save by shifting heating to off-peak hours?”

The Digital Twin engine contextualises queries with trends and comparative baselines, while ensuring privacy and compliance with data regulations. The result is increased consumer empowerment, actionable insights for efficiency, and enhanced user trust.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

In the baseline scenario, users do not have access to complex, automated energy insights within the existing application. Energy information is limited to basic consumption or cost data, without deeper analysis, contextualization, or personalised recommendations. There is also no NLP functionality, meaning users cannot interact through natural language queries and must rely solely on static or manually accessible information, resulting in low engagement and limited understanding of their energy patterns. Currently, no backend mechanisms exist to generate advanced insights, correlate data streams, or translate them into user-friendly explanations. To realise this UC, the system requires NLP integration, insight-generation pipelines, and Digital Twin-based contextualisation to deliver meaningful, personalised guidance to users.

LL5_UC4 - Promote Long-Term User Engagement through In-App Nudging

Scope of Use Case

This UC integrates nudging techniques into the EU-DREAM mobile app to encourage sustainable energy practices. Personalised notifications and recommendations guide consumers toward efficient energy behaviours, ensuring long-term engagement while supporting cost reduction and grid efficiency.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Increase engagement via personalised nudges and gamification.
- **Obj2:** Empower users with actionable real-time insights.
- **Obj3:** Maximise efficiency by optimising heating and energy use.
- **Obj4:** Promote sustainable consumption aligned with EU decarbonization goals.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2, BO3, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

The EU-DREAM mobile app delivers in-app nudges to sustain user engagement, guide decision-making, and encourage long-term energy savings.

This UC integrates behavioural nudging into the EU-DREAM ecosystem. Users receive tailored notifications, insights, and gamified challenges through the app. For example:

- “Shift heating to 10 PM for extra savings.”
- “You saved 15% more energy than your neighbourhood average this week!”

These nudges are based on real-time consumption, user profiles, and optimisation outputs. The system continuously adapts nudging strategies using behavioural data, increasing relevance and effectiveness. By linking nudges with heating controls (heat pumps, gas boilers), users can easily accept or decline suggestions, ensuring agency. This approach builds long-term engagement, reduces emissions, and strengthens consumer participation in the energy transition.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

Similar activities have been implemented within the [H2020 Nudge](#) and [DEDALUS projects](#). The achieved energy savings due to nudging were verified to be on average $\pm 3\%$ for the treatment group. However, certain homes managed to reduce their consumption by up to 16%. Even users who never use the DOMX smartphone application are able to efficiently heat their household and achieve both energy savings and thermal comfort by providing only their room target preferences through the simple DOMX wireless thermostat. As a result, DOMX users are able to achieve significant savings without requiring any interaction with the controller or the app. Thus, it is typical for users to have low motivation for interacting with a smartphone application, given the fact that they already experience significant energy savings and thermal comfort through a solution that does not require any interaction from them.

LL6

LL6_UC1 - DT-enabled Solutions for Smart Houses' Energy Management

Scope of Use Case

- Real-time optimisation of energy consumption and generation in residential homes using Digital Twin (DT) models.
- Non-intrusive load monitoring and effective control of smart appliances and renewable sources.
- Integration of local DT instances with the EU-DREAM ecosystem through the data broker.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Provide users with smart energy management solutions that reduce costs while maintaining or enhancing indoor comfort.
- **Obj2:** Empower users to control and optimise their energy consumption in real time through intuitive, AI-driven recommendations and NLP interaction.
- **Obj3:** Ensure users can easily manage and coordinate different smart devices and services through a unified, interoperable system that connects the DT layer and the AI assistant.

Related Business Case(s)

BO2, BO3, BO4

Narrative of Use Case

Digital Twin (DT) simulations drive this UC to optimise energy use in residential buildings. The DT serves as a dynamic virtual replica of the physical system, updated with real-time sensor data. It continuously simulates building behaviour under varying operational and environmental conditions. Scenario-based simulations evaluate the impact of control actions before real-world execution. The DT models interactions among appliances, HVAC, batteries, and renewables (e.g., PV systems). Predictive simulations support anticipatory energy management based on occupancy and weather forecasts. The DT enables optimal scheduling of energy resources to balance comfort and efficiency. All system behaviour is validated in simulation to ensure safe and effective operation. A FIWARE-compliant IoT platform ensures seamless real-time data exchange with the DT. The solution integrates into the EU-DREAM ecosystem via a standardised context broker.

As a resident in a smart home integrated with the EU-DREAM system, I do not need to manually manage when my appliances run or how I use electricity. Everything happens automatically and in real time. Through a simple app or voice interface, I can express my comfort preferences, such as maintaining a specific room temperature or reducing noise during certain hours. These preferences are interpreted using an NLP tool that communicates them to a DT model of my house.

This DT, which mirrors my home's energy profile, simulates and analyses my energy usage, forecasts consumption and production (if I have solar panels or other means of distributed generation), and works with AI algorithms to suggest optimal usage patterns that keep me comfortable while saving costs.

The underlying system operates through a local IoT platform based on FIWARE, which connects to my smart plugs, appliances, and renewable energy sources. Decisions and actions, like when to run my dishwasher or charge my battery, are made by the system in real time, based on both simulated scenarios and real-time data. This entire setup connects to the larger EU-DREAM ecosystem, ensuring that my house is both energy efficient and part of a smarter European grid. The assumption here is that my home is equipped with smart energy infrastructure and that I trust the system to manage my energy with minimal human intervention.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

An open-source IoT architecture, built upon the FIWARE framework, is currently operational at LL6. This platform is responsible for acquiring and persisting data from a diverse range of energy assets, while also being planned to serve as the host environment for the DT models and core infrastructure comprising EU-DREAM's solution. Furthermore, the IoT platform facilitates bidirectional data exchange with higher-level energy management systems, enabling seamless integration with both AI-driven and conventional planning and scheduling algorithms. This UC leverages the existing IoT-based communication infrastructure, which is already deployed and functioning as the local implementation.

It needs comprehensively developed DT models provided by work package 2 (WP2, Task 2.1), along with a fully implemented instance of the DT core infrastructure as defined in (Task 2.2, the AI optimisation tools (Task 2.3), and the NLP-based mediator (Task 2.4).

LL6_UC2 - Optimisation and Strategic Management of Energy Interactions with the Utility Grid

Scope of Use Case

- Enables grid-interactive operation via real-time bidirectional communication and actuation, supporting dynamic import/export of power using standard-compliant protocols.
- Employs advanced optimisation algorithms that leverage real-time and forecasted data market prices, load demand, PV generation, and storage state for optimal power scheduling.
- Integrates power electronics and storage systems, including bidirectional converters, battery energy storage systems (BESS), and smart meters, interfaced through low-throughput communication protocols such as ZigBee, LoRa, ... within the home IoT architecture.
- Complies with regulatory requirements and DSO interoperability, supporting EU grid codes and enabling API-based coordination for flexibility services, grid congestion management, and demand-side response (DSR) programs.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Empower prosumers to manage their energy generation and storage locally, supporting dynamic and reliable energy exchange with the grid.
- **Obj2:** Leverage AI-based forecasting and optimisation to help prosumers anticipate demand and generation, improving energy planning and efficiency.
- **Obj3:** Enable prosumers to reduce costs and enhance energy efficiency while supporting grid stability and regulatory compliance.
- **Obj4:** Provide prosumers with advanced market interfaces and analytics, enabling secure participation in P2P energy trading and flexibility services.

Related Business Case(s)

BO2, BO3

Narrative of Use Case

This UC orchestrates grid-interactive energy flows using AI-driven forecasting and optimisation algorithms based on multi-horizon predictions of load demand, photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbine generation, and electricity market prices. Bidirectional power converters and battery energy storage systems (BESS) are managed via real-time scheduling models (e.g., MPC, MILP), enabling dynamic import/export operations. Battery State-of-Charge (SoC) and State-of-Health (SoH) are continuously monitored to ensure safe, efficient, and degradation-aware dispatch. The system ensures regulatory compliance through standardised DSO interfaces (e.g., IEC 61850, ...), enabling participation in ancillary service markets. All assets—including wind, solar, storage, and smart loads—are integrated within a FIWARE-based IoT architecture using NGSI-LD context management for real-time control, interoperability, and autonomous grid interactions.

As a smart prosumer, my home energy system is now fully integrated into a grid-interactive architecture, enabling autonomous participation in residential energy trading. Equipped with battery energy storage systems (BESS), bidirectional converters, smart meters, and distributed generation assets (e.g., PV and wind), my home can dynamically import or export electricity based on real-time grid conditions and market signals. The system, deployed under the EU-DREAM framework, utilises AI-powered optimisation algorithms and multi-horizon forecasting models to predict consumption, generation, and electricity prices.

Decisions on whether to charge or discharge the battery, consume locally, or sell surplus energy to the grid are made automatically, using predictive control strategies. These decisions are constrained by technical factors, including battery State-of-Charge (SoC) and State-of-Health (SoH), while ensuring compliance with operational limits of power electronic interfaces and distribution grid codes.

All device coordination and control signals are transmitted via a FIWARE-based IoT infrastructure, leveraging NGSI-LD context models for semantic interoperability among devices, sensors, and control agents. I am not required to monitor the market or grid manually; the system maintains continuous synchronisation with Distribution System Operators (DSOs) via standardised protocols (e.g., IEC 61850, etc.) to support regulatory-compliant participation in demand response and ancillary service markets.

This capability presumes that my household infrastructure meets baseline interoperability requirements and that I operate within a regulatory and economic environment that enables residential prosumer participation in dynamic energy markets.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

LL6 consists of renewable energy sources, loads, and energy storage systems, which are electrically interconnected and communicate through the FIWARE-based IoT architecture. Although the bidirectional grid-connection converters are already installed and operational within the electrical setup, they are not yet fully integrated into the existing IoT infrastructure, requiring additional work to expose their data, control interfaces, and communication capabilities. Furthermore, LL6 requires the implementation of AI-driven optimisation algorithms and their seamless integration into the LL6 IoT architecture to enable real-time monitoring, intelligent control, and enhanced interoperability across all system components.

LL6_UC3 – Enhanced Load Scheduling in Residential Settings

Scope of Use Case

- Intelligent, real-time scheduling of household appliances based on:
 - User preferences (via NLP intermediary)
 - AI-based energy optimisation
- Differentiation between controllable and non-controllable loads.
- Use of decision-making models that allow users to reconcile user comfort with energy efficiency.
- Direct control of loads through IoT-based infrastructure and smart devices.

Objectives

- **Obj1:** Enable users to benefit from AI and Digital Twin tools that optimise home energy use in real time while respecting individual preferences and constraints.
- **Obj2:** Ensure user intentions are always respected by reconciling AI-generated schedules with preferences expressed through natural language interactions.
- **Obj3:** Adapt system behaviour continuously to users' evolving habits, comfort needs, and changing household conditions.
- **Obj4:** Empower users with intuitive control interfaces, comfort settings, and transparent explanations of AI-driven energy decisions.

Related Business Case(s)

BO1, BO2

Narrative of Use Case

This UC enables real-time residential load scheduling by integrating AI-based optimisation with user preferences acquired via NLP interfaces. Controllable loads (e.g., HVAC, EV charging) are scheduled dynamically, while non-controllable loads are modelled as fixed boundary conditions. The AI engine applies forecast-driven models to optimise energy cost and comfort within operational limits. A dedicated reconciliation layer evaluates conflicts between AI-generated schedules and user intents, applying rule-based or priority-weighted logic to enforce constraints, override decisions, or adapt preferences in real time. Final control actions are dispatched via the smart home IoT stack using standard protocols such as MQTT and Zigbee, ensuring interoperability with diverse devices. The system delivers adaptive and user-aligned energy scheduling for residential environments.

In my smart home, I no longer need to manually manage when appliances run, whether it is charging my devices, running the washing machine, or scheduling the dishwasher. The EU-DREAM system handles this through an intelligent, AI-driven load scheduling engine that operates in real time. During setup, I define my usage patterns, comfort preferences, and essential appliance constraints via a natural language interface, which translates my inputs into machine-readable parameters using the system's NLP-based intermediary.

Once configured, the system continuously monitors dynamic electricity prices, local energy consumption forecasts, and on-site renewable generation (like rooftop solar and residential-scale wind turbines), using predictive models to determine optimal schedules for controllable loads. These include appliances connected through smart plugs, Zigbee-enabled devices, or directly to the home energy management system.

Importantly, a reconciliation layer ensures that automated decisions reflect my preferences. It acts as a policy-aware arbitration module that resolves conflicts between AI-optimised schedules and user intent, using priority rules and contextual thresholds. For instance, even if the system detects low prices at night, it will not delay tasks I have marked as time sensitive. Once resolved, the final schedule is transmitted to devices over a FIWARE-based IoT infrastructure, using context data managed through the Orion Context Broker.

This entire orchestration assumes that my devices are interoperable, communicative, and that I retain soft control over my environment—enabling an energy system that is autonomous yet responsive to human input, without compromising comfort or convenience.

Baselines/Gaps/Needs

LL6 consists of different types of schedulable and non-schedulable residential loads (white goods and brown goods), and energy storage systems, which are electrically interconnected and communicate through the FIWARE-based IoT architecture. It needs the full development of the EU-DREAM AI assistant tools (Task 2.3) and also the NLP-based intermediary (Task 2.4) and their integration into the currently operating asset management system.

Conclusion

Task 1.4 has defined and formalised the methodological framework for identifying, describing, and classifying UCs within the EU-DREAM project, ensuring a consistent and interoperable approach across all LLs. The adopted methodology, based on IEC 62559-2 standard, provides a structured process for documenting actors, interactions, system functionalities, requirements, and performance indicators.

The developed UCs encompass both technical and social (co-creation) dimensions, capturing not only the system functionalities and platform capabilities but also the behavioural, organisational, and participatory aspects that characterise the LL environments. This dual perspective ensures that the EU-DREAM platform development remains aligned with user needs, regulatory contexts, and real-world operating conditions.

Task 1.4 concludes with a comprehensive and standardised UC framework that will serve as a reference for the design, implementation, and validation of the EU-DREAM platform in the upcoming Work Packages. It provides the methodological foundation for the development and evaluation of system architecture, integration activities, and demonstration phases within the project's LLs. The UCs defined in D1.4 will be implemented and tested in real-world conditions. The next stages of the project will translate these UCs into action through Work Package 7 (WP7), where the concepts and solutions outlined in D1.4 will be implemented and validated.

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